

Working fluid/oil separation in a reversible ORC test rig with a twin-screw machine: Lessons learned and remaining challenges

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ABSTRACT

Reversible Organic Rankine Cycles (rev. ORCs) offer the flexibility to operate either as power generators in ORC mode or as high-temperature heat pumps (HTHP) using the same reversible machine. This study builds upon recent initial experimental data obtained from a novel rev. ORC test rig at the *Technical University of Munich*. During the early commissioning phase, insufficient performance of the oil separator was observed due to an undersized design, leading to inadequate oil supply, particularly in ORC mode, which resulted in suboptimal machine operation. Thus, a detailed in-depth assessment has been carried out. Characterization of the oil system revealed that stable operation was only achievable at higher pressures and working fluid mass flow rates when oil supply to the expander was limited. Additionally, experimental campaigns in HTHP mode demonstrated that increasing the oil mass flow rate to the reversible compressor significantly improved volumetric machine efficiency. At lower thermal loads, volumetric efficiency increased by an average of 19.3 %, whereas improvements of 11.6 % were recorded at higher thermal loads. These findings indicate a stronger impact of elevated oil flow at lower compressor speeds and corresponding lower working fluid mass flow rates. Further experimental investigations with a new installed larger oil separator and refinements in oil monitoring and management are planned to enhance the understanding of this novel system.

1. MOTIVATION AND CONTRIBUTION

Reversible Organic Rankine Cycle (rev. ORC) systems have garnered increasing research interest in recent years. Their applications in domestic systems (Dumont *et al.*, 2015) and Carnot batteries (Weitzer *et al.*, 2023) have been widely studied. In the context of utilizing geothermal heat in combined heat and power plants, operating such systems as high-temperature heat pumps (HTHP) can help meet peak-load heating demands in district heating networks (DHN), thereby replacing fossil-fuel boilers. During periods of lower heat demand, the system can operate as an ORC to generate additional electrical power, enhancing economic profitability and reducing idle times. By employing the same machine flexibly as either a compressor or an expander, investment costs can be significantly reduced. Kaufmann *et al.* (2023) have proposed such a system, which has been designed and constructed at the *Technical University of Munich* (TUM) in recent years.

Twin-screw compressors and expanders are widely used in HTHP and ORC systems for small- to medium-scale applications due to their durability and favorable displacement-based operation. In oil-injected variants, lubrication is essential not only for sealing and wear reduction but also for thermal management, particularly in high-temperature processes (Abdan *et al.*, 2019). However, improper oil supply can lead to significant efficiency losses. Yusha *et al.* (2017) showed that optimal oil injection minimizes losses to below 10 %, whereas suboptimal injection can cause drops of up to 40 %. Wu *et al.* (2017) further emphasized the importance of injection position and oil temperature, identifying

both as key parameters for efficient operation. Recent CFD studies by Basha *et al.* (2021) confirmed the performance impact of oil injection strategies, showing that multi-port injection improves oil distribution and reduces gas temperatures, thus enhancing volumetric efficiency. Similar conclusions were drawn by Yang *et al.* (2019) and Van Nieuwenhuysse *et al.* (2020) for expanders in ORC systems, who demonstrated improved isentropic and overall system efficiencies with increased oil content and effective lubrication. Accurate oil dosing and minimal carryover require efficient separation and reliable oil management. In conventional refrigeration and heat pump systems, separators are typically placed between the compressor outlet and the condenser, enabling immediate separation, cooling, and reinjection of oil (Majgaonkar *et al.*, 2020). The higher pressure and density on the high-pressure side reduce volumetric flow, allowing for more compact separator designs. For ORC systems, Lei *et al.* (2014) compare different separator placements and show that positioning it upstream of the expander on the high-pressure side offers improved oil flow control, lower pressure losses and reduced complexity. Steger *et al.* (2021) confirm these findings for integrated HP/ORC Carnot battery systems by adopting the same separator configuration, placing it downstream of the compressor in HTHP mode and upstream of the expander in ORC mode.

Despite these insights, experimental investigations on oil supply remain limited, especially in reversible systems. The authors of this work recently presented the first characterization of a reversible ORC test rig at TUM, revealing restricted machine efficiencies due to oil supply limitations and an insufficient separation system (Kaufmann *et al.*, 2025). In response, a new separator was implemented to improve oil management. This work builds on those findings, evaluating the performance of the original oil separator in ORC mode and examining the influence of oil flow on machine efficiency. The results contribute to a deeper understanding of the newly developed rev. ORC system with focus on oil management and are highly relevant to the research community.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Test rig description and oil issue

In the following section, the test rig and oil-related issues are described. Following Figure 1 depicts a simplified P&ID of the whole process. The test rig is supplied by a $200 \text{ kW}_{\text{th}}$ hot water heating circuit, serving as the heat source. A closed-loop intermediate cooling circuit allows the simulation of a DHN with varying temperature levels and mass flows during HTHP operation. The heat source temperature (T_{HS}) for ORC operation spans a range between 90°C and 140°C . Conversely, the heat sink temperature ranges from 80°C to 120°C in HTHP mode, using heat source temperatures between 40°C and 95°C . The low-GWP refrigerant R1233zd(E) is used as working fluid. To get a detailed description of the whole process, the reader is invited to read the publication by Kaufmann *et al.* (2025).

The test rig incorporates a modified, fully reversible $20 \text{ kW}_{\text{mech}}$ open twin-screw machine (*Bitzer OSK 5361-K*). As lubricating oil *Reniso Triton CE500* by *Fuchs Lubricants Germany GmbH* is used. For effective oil separation and dosing, an additional oil circuit with an oil separator-collector (OSC) was implemented into the test rig using a *BOS2-R-35F* by *ESK Schultze*. The manufacturer claims a separation efficiency of approximately 97% to 99%, depending on the operating conditions. In addition, a sight glass was installed after the OSC outlet in order to observe the phase state of the working fluid. In HTHP operation, the oil-laden, superheated working fluid vapor passes through the OSC immediately after the compression stage, where oil and working fluid are largely separated. The recovered oil is then directed to the bearings and screw profiles, being injected into the suction gas for the latter purpose. In ORC operation, however, the oil-laden working fluid first circulates through the entire system after expansion, including all relevant components such as heat exchangers (HEX). Although the effects of oil accumulation and other phenomena in the heat exchangers were already considered during the design phase, this configuration remains the most suitable for the reversible system. Furthermore, alternating the inlet and outlet streams of the OSC is challenging, as the internal flow direction of the component cannot be reversed. Oil and working fluid separation takes place at a high-pressure level between evaporator and expander, which is consistent with configurations proposed in the literature. In this mode,

oil dosing was applied only to the expander's bearings, as the amount of oil carried with the working fluid, due to insufficient separation, was already considered as sufficient. However, the system includes a solenoid valve for direct oil injection into the expander profiles, which should remain open under improved separation performance of the new OSC to ensure adequate lubrication. Downstream of the separator, an oil pump supports flow in ORC mode by compensating for pressure losses, while in HTHP mode, the pressure gradient from the compressor allows for bypassing the pump. Initial tests showed that bypassing the pump in ORC mode did not restrict oil flow. The oil then passes through a filter to remove potential contaminants.

The separation technology applied in this study operates on the coalescence principle, employing glass fiber microfilter elements within dedicated cartridges as the filtration medium (FM). Figure 2 presents a simplified schematic of the OSC where the upper half represents the separator and the lower half the collector part of the unit. At the inlet, the oil-laden working fluid ($\dot{m}_{wf,in,ol}$) enters the OSC in a superheated state. As it passes through the FM (represented by a meshed rectangle), the oil separates from the working fluid and accumulates in the collector section due to gravitational effects (\dot{m}_{os}). The oil-free working fluid then exits the separator ($\dot{m}_{wf,out,of}$) while remaining in a superheated state. However, since the OSC does not achieve perfect separation efficiency, small traces of oil remain in the working fluid at the outlet. Consequently, in practical applications, the outlet vapor is better described as oil-reduced rather than completely oil-free. The separated oil, which still contains a certain amount of dissolved working fluid due to the good solubility of the given refrigerant-oil mixture, then returns to the machine (\dot{m}_{or}).

Figure 1: Simplified P&ID of the constructed reversible ORC test rig with parts of the heating circuit. Main control loops for ORC (red) and HTHP (blue) operation system. The oil separating unit is located on the upper left side in between evaporator and rev. machine. (Kaufmann *et al.*, 2025)

After the first operational hours, several observations indicated an insufficient oil separation:

1. **High liquid content after OSC.** A liquid was observed in the sight glass downstream of the OSC. Given that the working fluid remains in a superheated state under these conditions, this liquid is most likely entrained oil. While a small amount is expected due to the separator's non-ideal efficiency, significant liquid accumulation suggests inadequate separation performance and an undersized FM.
2. **Excessive pressure losses.** Experimental data revealed that the pressure drop across the OSC unit was significant, reaching up to 1 bar at certain operating points. The manufacturer states that losses above 0.8 bar are atypical, while coalescing cartridge-based separation typically results in losses around 0.3 bar. The substantially higher observed values indicate an undersized FM, causing excessive flow resistance for the given volumetric flows.
3. **Limitations in ORC mode.** Low separation efficiency resulted in an insufficient oil level in the separator's collector, restricting oil supply to the reversible machine and preventing tests with higher oil injection rates to assess their impact on expander efficiency. The issue was particularly pronounced in ORC mode, where oil circulation times are significantly longer. As a result, the oil does not return quickly enough to establish a stable level at higher \dot{m}_{or} and low separation efficiencies, limiting oil flow to prevent dry running of the collector. A larger oil collector and an increased overall oil quantity would therefore be beneficial. In contrast, this issue does not occur in heat pump mode, where oil circulation times are much shorter and the impact of poor separation is less significant, as the primary oil circulation is confined to a much smaller part of the overall system.

Figure 2: Simplified scheme of the Oil separator-collector with corresponding mass flow rates.

2.2 Experimental procedure and evaluation

In the following sections the experimental procedure for the OSC characterization as well as for the oil influence on machine efficiencies are going to be presented.

To evaluate the performance of the original oil separator and analyze the influence of various operating parameters on separation efficiency, a series of experiments was conducted. These tests were designed to force the OSC to run dry, allowing measurement of the time until this condition occurred. This approach enables identification of the most influential parameters and provides a basis for direct comparison with the newly implemented OSC in future studies. The experimental methodology followed the initial system characterization by Kaufmann *et al.* (2025), in which evaporation pressure (p_{evap}), pump speed (n_{pump}) and T_{HS} were varied. In the present study, heat source mass flow was kept constant at 1.0 kg/s, while p_{evap} was adjusted between 8 and 9 bar. Here, evaporation pressure was controlled through modulation of the expander rotational speed. A decrease in expander speed led to an increase in evaporation pressure under constant pump operating conditions. Additionally, \dot{m}_{or} was systematically

varied between 10 g/s and 30 g/s in 5 g/s increments, corresponding to oil mass fractions ranging from 2.8 to 15 %, depending on the working fluid mass flows, which varied between 200 and 360 g/s. However, in most cases, only lower returned oil mass flow values were achievable. It is important to note that the mass flow was measured between the working fluid pump and the evaporator (see FR21 in Figure 1), meaning that in ORC mode, the total mass flow of the oil-working fluid mixture was recorded. Each measurement was terminated after 500 s, by which time either a quasi-steady state had been reached or the system was not able to stabilize.

To assess the impact of oil injection on machine efficiency, the system characterization approach from Kaufmann *et al.* (2025) was again employed. To achieve a finer resolution and maximize the operational limits, a lift-variation approach was chosen instead of an application-based scenario. In this methodology, the temperature spread in the DHN was maintained at a constant 10 K, while the lift was incrementally increased in 10 K steps, corresponding return temperatures ranging from 70 °C to 100 °C. The DHN mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{DHN}) was varied among 0.5 kg/s, 1.0 kg/s and 1.5 kg/s. Additionally, \dot{m}_{or} was increased by 10 g/s per test sequence, starting at 15 g/s and ending at the maximum achievable value ($\dot{m}_{\text{or,max}}$). This upper limit represents the highest attainable oil mass flow at a given compressor speed with 100 % oil pump capacity engaged. As the returned oil mass flow increases with compressor speed, the maximum returned oil mass flow ranged between 33 and 43 g/s at lower compressor speed and DHN duties, while at higher speeds, it varied between 32 and 55 g/s. These values define the current system limitations, which cannot be exceeded under the given conditions. It is suspected that at elevated compressor speed, the current oil pump fails to offer any significant advantage over operation without the pump. In fact, it may introduce additional flow resistance, thereby limiting the oil flow. This suggests that the pump is most likely undersized and for further experiments, a larger model will be required. As previously mentioned, a similar investigation in ORC mode was not possible, as stable operation at elevated returned oil mass flows could not be maintained over extended periods. In both operating modes, the oil was cooled to 70 °C.

This study focuses exclusively on machine performance in HTHP mode, as the experimental operation of ORC mode is significantly restricted due to limitations in oil supply, preventing the same level of flexibility in testing, as previously mentioned. To evaluate the overall performance of an HTHP process from an energetic perspective, the coefficient of performance (COP) is typically used, representing the ratio of heating output to electrical power input. However, this indicator is not considered in this work, as future studies will place a stronger emphasis on this aspect. For assessing compressor performance, the volumetric efficiency is used as the primary indicator:

$$\eta_{\text{vol}} = \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{su}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{su,id}}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{wf}}}{n_{\text{comp}} \cdot V_{\text{sw,comp}} \cdot \rho_{\text{su}}}. \quad (1)$$

This metric quantifies the impact of internal leakages by comparing the actual volumetric flow at the compressor inlet with the theoretical flow, calculated from the swept volume ($V_{\text{sw,comp}}$) and rotational speed (n_{comp}). The actual flow is derived from the mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{wf}) and density at the suction side (ρ_{su}). While isentropic efficiency is often used to assess compressor performance, it was excluded here due to unrealistically high values and uncertainties arising from non-adiabatic effects and imperfect insulation. Volumetric efficiency alone does not fully characterize the compressor's performance but strongly influences the operational range and heating output of the given system. Moreover, the authors' previous publication showed only a partial correlation between mechanical and volumetric efficiency, underlining the need for further investigation. In this study, however, volumetric efficiency is considered the most relevant parameter for evaluating and optimizing HTHP operation. Since the actual oil content is unknown due to incomplete separation, no correction of volumetric flow was applied. Data processing followed the approach of Kaufmann *et al.* (2025) and Gaussian error propagation was applied to account for sensor inaccuracies. For the ORC experiments, uncertainty analysis was omitted for clarity, as the relative error in level measurement and signal processing was deemed negligible.

3. CHARACTERIZATION AND MODIFICATION OF THE OIL SYSTEM

Figure 3 illustrates the dry running behavior of the OSC in ORC mode for given parameters at T_{HS} of 110°C (a) and 130°C (b). To maintain the scope of this study, the analysis is focused solely on operating points with \dot{m}_{or} of 15 g/s . The slope of the curves represents the dry running velocity of the OSC, while the theoretical limit (black line) defines the maximum possible velocity, serving as a threshold that cannot be exceeded. This limit was derived from the volumetric flow rate of the oil, considering its density and the diameter of the OSC's cylindrical body, under the assumption that \dot{m}_{or} significantly exceeds the separated oil mass flow, indicating that the oil-laden working fluid mass flow is negligibly small in comparison to \dot{m}_{or} . The relative oil level was calculated based on the measurement range of the sensor lance. Due to the rapid dry running and the slow refilling process between measurements, a full oil level (100 %) could not be reached for every operating point. Instead, an initial level of 70 % was set to allow sufficient time for critical parameters such as evaporation pressure and oil temperature to stabilize before measurements commenced. A lower threshold of 5 % was defined to prevent the rev. machine from running completely dry.

Figure 3: Oil level over time for given evaporation pressures and pump speeds at T_{HS} of 110°C (a) and 130°C (b). Pump speed is varied between 25 %, 35 % and 45 % of the maximum speed of 1800 rpm.

The results indicate that an increase in p_{evap} enhances separation efficiency, leading to a slower dry running of the OSC. A similar effect is observed with increasing pump speed, though p_{evap} appears to have a more pronounced influence. At higher p_{evap} , a quasi-equilibrium state is achieved even at a lower pump speed of 35 %, enabling stable operation. The curves corresponding to the lowest pump speeds exhibit the steepest slopes, converging toward the theoretical limit. It should be noted that a returned oil mass flow of 15 g/s is relatively low and insufficient for efficient expander operation. However, tests with higher oil mass flow rates did not result in stable operation.

A potential explanation for improved separation at higher pressures is the reduction in volumetric flow rate resulting from the increased density of the working fluid vapor. This leads to lower vapor velocities at the coalescence filter interface and longer residence times within the filtration medium, both of which promote coalescence. Here, a pressure increase from 8 to 9 bar under the given mass flow conditions reduced the volumetric flow rate by approximately 0.6 to 1.2 L/s, corresponding to a relative change of 13 %. While a higher working fluid mass flow generally results in increased vapor velocities, potentially impairing separation, it simultaneously increases the oil mass flow rate at the OSC inlet and reduces oil residence time in the working fluid cycle. This effect ultimately leads to an increase in separated oil mass flow (\dot{m}_{os} in Figure 2). Thus, the combination of higher working fluid mass flow rates and elevated operating pressure may contribute to more stable and efficient separation performance.

Another possible explanation is the improved solubility of the refrigerant in oil at higher pressures, which could lead to co-separation of additional liquid working fluid. Dawo (2024) investigated the solubility behavior of refrigerants in machine oil and found that higher pressures increase working fluid solubility, potentially leading to greater entrainment of liquid working fluid during separation, falsely inflating \dot{m}_{os} . However, the mentioned study did not consider superheated working fluid vapor and used a different oil with distinct solubility properties. Moreover, at the high superheating levels observed in the present system (16 to 20 K at 110 °C and 36 to 41 K at 130 °C), refrigerant solubility in oil is expected to have only a minimal effect on the vapor-phase partial pressure and is unlikely to cause significant measurement distortion. Additionally, an external heating strap around the OSC prevents local oil cooling, reducing the likelihood of refrigerant condensation. However, a minor influence cannot be entirely ruled out under real-world conditions and further experimental investigations would be necessary to fully quantify this effect. In general, stable operation was not achieved at elevated T_{HS} , despite the lowest dry-running velocities being observed at high pressures and pump speeds. A potential reason is the very small pinch point in the evaporator due to the oversized HEX surface, causing the outlet temperature of the working fluid/oil mixture to approach T_{HS} . Consequently, the volumetric flow of both fluids increases and the oil viscosity is significantly reduced at higher temperatures. Additionally, the lower viscosity at elevated T_{HS} could result in finer oil atomization, increasing the likelihood of oil entrainment in the separated vapor stream, ultimately reducing separation efficiency.

The findings highlight a significant undersizing of the original OSC, prompting its replacement with a larger unit. To address this limitation, the *BOS2-R-54F* model from the same manufacturer was selected, offering an expanded coalescence cartridge and a collector volume of 6.1 L, more than doubling the capacity of the previous design. While the installation has already been successfully completed, operation will commence subsequent to the completion of this paper. As a result, no experimental data are available yet to assess potential performance enhancements with the new oil separator.

4. INFLUENCE OF THE OIL SUPPLY ON THE MACHINE EFFICIENCY

This section focuses on analyzing the impact of oil supply on volumetric machine efficiency. The experiments were conducted using the original OSC. Figure 4 presents the volumetric efficiencies as a function of the pressure difference across the compressor (Δp_{comp}), which serves as the driving force behind leakage losses. A higher Δp_{comp} corresponds to an increased n_{comp} . To illustrate this effect, only results for \dot{m}_{DHN} of 0.5 kg/s and 1.5 kg/s are shown, representing the lower and upper thermal loads. These affect the working fluid mass flow demand and thereby the compressor speed required to meet the load. For test sequences at maximum oil flow, additional data points were recorded at 5 K lift increments to achieve finer resolution. Due to time constraints, this refinement was not applied to test series with lower oil flow rates. Additionally, for a \dot{m}_{DHN} of 0.5 kg/s, the target oil mass flow of 35 g/s was not attained at lower compressor speeds. As a result, the maximum achievable \dot{m}_{or} , slightly below this target, was defined as maximum value (yellow curve in Figure 4a) and the corresponding data points were subsequently excluded from the 35 g/s curve for consistency. Figure 5 illustrates the volumetric efficiency as a function of compressor speed. The behavior of the curves for different oil mass flows closely resembles those presented in Figure 4, reflecting the close relationship between compressor speed, pressure differential and volumetric efficiency at different thermal loads.

At both DHN mass flows, η_{vol} is lowest at small pressure differentials and increases with rising Δp_{comp} and, consequently, n_{comp} . At higher DHN mass flows and thermal loads, volumetric efficiency exhibits a steady but moderate increase with Δp_{comp} . In contrast, at 0.5 kg/s, a much steeper increase is observed, reaching a maximum at a pressure difference of 6 to 7 bar or compressor speeds of 1025 to 1100 rpm, followed by a decline. This initial increase can be attributed to the generally positive effect of higher rotational speeds on volumetric efficiency. While a rising pressure differential typically leads to lower volumetric efficiencies at constant speed, an increase in n_{comp} at a fixed pressure differential enhances η_{vol} . This effect arises because, as \dot{m}_{wf} increases with n_{comp} , the relative impact of internal leakage mass flow diminishes, thereby improving volumetric efficiency. However, elevated rotor speeds also impose

Figure 4: Volumetric efficiency over pressure difference of the compressor for varying oil return mass flows at a DHN mass flow rate of 0.5 kg/s (a) and 1.5 kg/s (b).

Figure 5: Volumetric efficiency over rotational speed of the compressor for varying oil return mass flows at a DHN mass flow rate of 0.5 kg/s (a) and 1.5 kg/s (b).

higher shear rates and mechanical stresses on the oil film, potentially destabilizing it. Consequently, as Δp_{comp} rises in conjunction with increasing speed, a decline in η_{vol} is observed at lower thermal loads, suggesting that further speed increases would likely exacerbate this effect. This shear-induced film destabilization is considered the primary cause for the efficiency drop under the given oil supply conditions. Importantly, the decline in η_{vol} at higher Δp_{comp} is not attributed directly to pressure differential itself, but rather to the associated increase in compressor speed. In general, the lubrication efficiency appears to be superior at lower thermal loads and therefore reduced compressor speeds. At higher thermal loads, the available oil supply is insufficient to adequately lubricate the rotor profiles, seal individual compression chambers and minimize leakage even at small pressure differentials (see Figure 4b). An increased oil supply is therefore essential at generally higher rotational speeds (see Figure 5b) to maintain effective compressor operation.

The influence of increased oil mass flow is particularly pronounced at lower thermal loads, where η_{vol} reaches up to 84 % at maximum \dot{m}_{or} , yielding average relative improvements of approximately 19.3 % compared to the lowest oil mass flows. At higher thermal loads, the absolute impact of increased oil supply appears less significant, with peak values of 59 % and relative improvements of 11.6 %. This

discrepancy can be attributed to the higher oil-to-working-fluid ratios at lower thermal loads, where maximum \dot{m}_{or} generally facilitates a more stable compressor operation. However, it is important to note that working fluid mass flow is measured between the throttle valve and the evaporator (see FR21 in Figure 1). Due to non-ideal oil separation, a portion of the injected oil remains in the process, leading to an overestimation of the measured refrigerant mass flow in HTHP mode. Consequently, this could result in an erroneous calculation of higher η_{vol} , as the volumetric flow rate is determined based on the pure refrigerant density rather than the actual mixture composition. This effect is particularly relevant at lower thermal loads, where the relative contribution of oil mass flow is higher, posing a potential source of error. Optimizing oil separation and implementing advanced oil monitoring with precise determination of the oil/working fluid composition would mitigate this issue and enhance measurement accuracy. Additionally, oil evaporation may influence sealing behavior and volumetric efficiency. However, due to a lack of vapor pressure data for the specific oil at operating conditions, this effect was not further investigated and is currently assumed to be of minor relevance. Thus, the results highlight further process improvement potential. Furthermore, η_{vol} continues to increase at maximum oil flow without signs of stagnation, indicating opportunities for advanced oil supply and refining oil dosing strategies.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

This study presents a comprehensive experimental investigation of oil separation behavior in rev. ORC systems, emphasizing the complex interactions between working fluid properties, oil characteristics and separator design. The findings reveal that the original oil separator was significantly undersized, leading to operational instability. Stable ORC operation was only achievable at higher pressures and mass flows due to reduced volumetric flow rates and increased residence times in the separator's filtration medium. As a result, the system could only operate reliably under specific conditions, highlighting the necessity of an enlarged oil separator. In addition, the impact of oil supply on compressor efficiency was analyzed. Results show the volumetric efficiency increased with oil mass flow and pressure differential due to the simultaneously rising compressor speed, particularly at lower thermal loads. Under these conditions, a peak volumetric efficiency of 84 % was observed, demonstrating substantial potential for performance optimization through enhanced oil supply and dosing strategies. At higher thermal loads, efficiency reached 59 %, reflecting a relative improvement of 11.6 %. These findings underscore the critical role of precise oil management in achieving optimal system performance, contributing to the further development of rev. ORC technology with twin-screw machines and its potential commercialization.

Future investigations will focus on improving oil separation efficiency and implementing advanced oil monitoring systems. The newly designed oil separator, once operational, is expected to provide deeper insights and enhanced performance data. Additional experiments with increased oil flow rates will be conducted to explore further optimization potential. Given that the current tests revealed limitations due to oil pump capacity, replacing it with a higher-capacity pump is a viable option. Furthermore, system modifications, including expanded measurement instrumentation, will enable precise determination of the oil–working fluid mixture composition and improving measurement accuracy. A more detailed evaluation of energetic aspects in both HTHP and ORC modes, particularly the influence of oil on heat transfer, will also be pursued. In addition, further methods to assess the performance of the reversible compressor will be explored. This includes accounting for heat losses across the compressor, enabling, for example, calculation of diabatic efficiency.

NOMENCLATURE

Latin Letters

\dot{m}	mass flow rate (kg/s or g/s)
COP	coefficient of performance (-)
DHN	district heating network
FM	filtration medium

HEX	heat exchanger
HS	heat source
$HTHP$	high temperature heat pump
n	rotational speed (rpm)
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle

<i>OSC</i>	oil separator-collector	<i>in</i>	inlet
<i>p</i>	pressure (bar)	<i>max</i>	maximum
<i>T</i>	temperature (K or °C)	<i>of</i>	oil-free
Greek Letters		<i>ol</i>	oil-laden
Δ	difference (-)	<i>or</i>	oil return
η	efficiency (- or %)	<i>os</i>	oil separated
ρ	Density (kg/m ³)	<i>out</i>	outlet
Subscripts		<i>su</i>	suction side
<i>comp</i>	compressor	<i>sw</i>	swept
<i>evap</i>	evaporation	<i>vol</i>	volumetric
<i>id</i>	ideal	<i>wf</i>	working fluid

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